

THE STATE OF THE ART ON THE EDUCATIONAL SOFTWARE TOOLS FOR ELECTROACOUSTIC COMPOSITION

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ABSTRACT

In the past twenty years technological development has led to an increasing interest in the employment of the information and communication technology (ICT) in music education. Research still indicates that most music teachers use technology to facilitate working in traditional composing contexts, such as score writing or MIDI keyboard sequencing, revealing a common and conservative conception of ICT as mere “toolkit” with limited application. Despite this, the exploration of the electroacoustic practices and their techniques, that are at the core of sound-based (as opposed to note-based) musical practices, have led to valuable composition projects thanks to pieces of software specifically created for educational purposes such as DSP by NOTAM and Compose with Sounds among others.

In this paper I will first give a short overview of the significant premises for an effective curriculum for middle and secondary education that can authentically include the electroacoustic composition, then I will summarize the state of the art in the development of the most significant educational software packages pointing to possible future developments.

1. INTRODUCTION

As we know from the last published PISA report (2012) the use of ICT positively supports results in core disciplines: in those countries where arts education is prioritized, students achieve better results in disciplines such as mathematics and physics.

Unfortunately, the effects of ICT tools employed in music education is under-researched (Rudi, 2013). It is a fact that studies in this area are mostly oriented towards note-based music and the tools that fit this approach. Despite this situation we are able to define the advantages created by the employment of electroacoustic practice in this context in the following fashion:

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- The possibility of direct manipulation of source material provides immediate feedback and implicit encouragement.
 - Allowing the use of synthesized sounds as well as a student’s own recordings, is not merely an act of encouragement where students provide their to own material, but as it has already been demonstrated (Harter, 1990), they will most likely be inclined to develop a long term interest in those activities that directly concern their personal and social identity, and more generally their emerging concepts of “self”.
 - Working with musical signal processing technology that deals with phenomena in the sounds themselves, leads to various degrees of awareness in the intrinsic properties of sound and their role in wider musical structures. In other words, a conscious sense of the musical form is developed through practice.
 - Digital tools through their very nature address cross-disciplinary projects in the broadest sense.
- Nonetheless all of this does not mean that all pedagogical aspects of musical ICT can be defined as appropriate. It is crucial to pay attention to those critical issues of music curriculum development in order to avoid an outcome whereby a significant art form loses its pedagogical potential.

2. A CLEAR PERSPECTIVE

2.1. Basic assumptions

The development of virtuosic electroacoustic practice within music education curricula has been slowed down by two phenomena: Firstly by the prevailing stereotypes and by weak conceptual elaborations, and secondly by the lack of a strong link between the processing of contents put into practice by musicology and the pedagogical concepts of music. Actually, in most cases, technology’s role is conceived exclusively in relation to a traditional music curriculum. This approach leads to a misunderstanding where composition based on sounds is seen as separate from “serious” composition based on notes (Martin, 2010).

We can better understand what causes this misinterpretation referring to two competing paradigms borrowed

from music pedagogy, representing two contrasting “*Weltanschauungen*”.

Martin (2010) and others have already debated the argument, therefore the scope of this article will be limited to the key statements in surrounding the development of a conceptual framework that details why electroacoustic practice can be authentically pursued thanks to educational software.

2.2. A critique of “Good Taste”

The paradigm labeled as “aesthetics” traces its origins to late eighteenth and early nineteenth century romantic idealism and has been the predominant conceptual basis for music pedagogy (Reimer, 1988 and others), and consequently in education, since the middle of the twentieth century (McCarthy and Goble, 2005). The focus of this paradigm is a definition of music comprising “aesthetic or expressive elements” which according to Reimer (1988, p.52) can be defined as “rhythm, melody, harmony, tone colour, texture and form”. Whether, musical activities in the classroom involve making or listening, this becomes aimed at understanding and developing these supposed intrinsic properties of musical works. In order to pursue these kinds of educational goals it becomes crucial to choose good examples of music, mostly Western art music, that supposedly have those universal qualities transcending all temporal, spatial, cultural, and social contexts. Since the education that is derived from these underlying assumptions is geared to develop sensitivity for the appreciation of musical works rather than the capacity for making music. The ideal student that should be trained, assuming that an adequate training can take place, is an expert connoisseur with a “Good taste” for a specific kind of music. Due to its nature, this approach leads to the imposition on the classroom of the aforementioned exercises instead of authentic activities, and therefore ultimately tends to fail to sufficiently involve students in music because it is not perceived as really meaningful by the students themselves.

2.3. The turning point

The focus of the praxial paradigm (Elliott, 1995) concerns practices. The emphasis shifts from the “musical objects” to the practices that produce those objects, from an ideal realm of universals to a web of social, cultural, economic and political attributes inside of which these practices take place. With these premises it becomes clear how musical meaning is in no small part inherent in the context in which the sound is produced instead of being an intrinsic value of the sound itself as the aesthetic perspective claims. The music is conceived as something people do, and therefore the different declinations of music-making such as composing, arranging, performing and improvising are the goals of an education based on this perspective. The curriculum becomes a *practicum* with the aim to approximate authentic music cultures not to duplicate them, and in which “rich and challenging music-making projects in classroom situations [...] are deliberately organized as close parallels to true musical practices” (Elliott, 1995, p. 261). Within this framework a more effective and authentic learning environment can be

accomplished for at least two reasons. First, the fact that students can learn through activities and problem-based situations rather than listening, makes the subject more accessible, better fitting the needs of pre-and early adolescents in their phase of development, and generally guaranteeing them better training as Lonsbury (2000) observed. Second, it is a matter of authenticity: if the music is presented merely as a school subject with activities directed to understand and to appreciate “the elements of music” the students tend to be less motivated because, as research indicates (Caskey and Anfara, 2007), young adolescents are typically drawn to real-life experiences and related learning situations that are perceived as authentic and meaningful.

3. HOW TO ACTUALIZE THE PRACTICE

The nature of electroacoustic music fits the basic assumptions of the praxial paradigm and its consequences. Researches in this direction as yet has not been undertaken and consequently there is much we do not know. My personal teaching experience led me to think that the *medium* to fully actualize the above mentioned premises should mostly be comprised of pieces of software specifically created for educational purposes for at least three reasons. Firstly, it is crucial to be able to create an educational environment that integrates conceptual and practical learning. The focus on practice does not necessarily need to lead to the misunderstanding, that conceptual learning is banned from this approach leaving the student free to find his or her own way through the possibilities enabled with the software package in question. Conceptual learning should be used to understand, to address and to facilitate the practice. The advantages of this approach are double: on the one hand, we do not run the risk of providing concepts that can be interpreted as detached from practice, since we can promptly verify conceptual notions. On the other hand, the teacher can scientifically supervise the progresses of the students learning. Second, as with regards to commercial pieces of software, with their own logic, which are geared towards professional or amateur users, they do not approximate an authentic music practice, but instead create it without mediation; the aim of music education is not to educate all students for careers as professional musicians. Eventually, what is not perceived as personally meaningful to the students is doomed to fail, even if it involves a creative attempt to interest them in electroacoustic music using the “fanciest” software. It is realistic to think that products based on the educational needs of the student offer tangible benefits related to his/her personal and social life as much as needed to continue to pursue the subject after the school years.

4. THE STATE OF THE ART

4.1. Preamble

If a “perfect tool” that includes all these features does not exist in order to teach electroacoustic music in middle and secondary school classes, the risk that these endeavours become their own means to an end in the service of a

curriculum geared towards music appreciation, is just around the corner. Nevertheless, valuable projects such as DSP, E-Lab/Live8 and Compose with Sounds represent steps in the right direction and they entail not only a correct practice, but they can also be taken as benchmarks in order to formulate possible future developments.

4.1.1. Common features

The reason why these projects embody an authentic and “correct” practice, as it has been outlined above, can be seen in the desirability of some of their characteristics.

- They get closer to professional pieces of software for music composition.
- They allow the exploration of sound and its properties through advanced and complementary software tools.
- They require a limited conceptual musical training providing at the same time a multilayered interactive help system (supported only on DSP and Compose with Sounds).
- They entail a constructivist approach with student-centered (but teacher supervised) learning perspective.
- They focus on relatively easy operations and an appealing graphic user interface (GUI).

The following section illustrates the different contexts where these pieces of software come from, as well as their specific characteristics.

4.2. DSP

Even though in the mid-90s there were few educational programs or general familiarity with music technology in

Figure 1. DSP screenshot of the mixing and editing windows.

Norway, the Ministry of Education developed guidelines for the employment of such technology in schools. Regarding music, children were supposed to compose using technology. The context of the birth of the project was pioneering because the digital revolution was only in its early stages and computers still had strong computational limits. DSP (Digital Sound Processing) has been the first software expressly created for educational purposes which was developed and maintained by the Norwegian Network for Technology, Acoustic and Music (NOTAM) from 1996 to 2013¹.

As we can clearly see in Fig. 1 the aim of the project was to develop a “software model for education that [...] resembles a professional software approach for computer composition, such as signal processing software [...] and screen based mixers (e.g. ProTools)” (Rudi, 2007). The mixer window (Fig. 1, background window) is composed of five tracks and some “classic” controllers, that screen-based mixers generally have, such as: playback and pan controllers, gain slider, the possibility to insert markers and to turn each track on or off and a menu bar. Both from the “Sound”, “Distortion” and “Effects” menus is possible to access to the sound processing algorithms (fig. 1, front page window) that include chorus, flanger, delay, harmonizer, filters, reverb, ring modulation, operations in the spectral domain, time stretching, granulation, scratch, as well as the possibility to generate sounds or musical structures from mathematical models; real-time processing of audio streams is not supported. Since DSP is no longer maintained it is not clear if it is still possible to connect it to the NOTAM website in order to read the tutorial texts accessible through the “Help” button in the editing window. During the past years this innovative approach to music education has enhanced the popularity of DSP thanks to music projects and workshops in Norway, Sweden, Denmark, UK, France, Portugal and Italy as it is demonstrated by the languages available for the software.

4.3. E-Lab and Live_8

The two Max-based² learning environments were developed at Tempo Reale, a technology-based music center for production, research and education, established in 1987 by Luciano Berio in Florence. From 1999 Berio started to promote the planning and the development of new educational activities focused on creative practices and aimed at 8 - 13 year old primary and middle school children, through the use of pieces of software specifically created for educational purposes. After an experimental phase ran at IRCAM-Centre G. Pompidou³, since 2000 the project has been developed and spread in many Italian

¹ Last available version is updated to february 2013, <http://archive.notam02.no/DSP02/>

² Max is a visual programming language for music and multimedia developed by Cycling'74, <http://cycling74.com>.

³ *Atelier Jeunes* created by T. Coduys and J. Baboni-Schilingi.

Figure 2. E-Lab screenshot.

cities, with the participation of more than 1700 students, and culminated between 2005 and 2007 in the realization, among others, of the final version of E-Lab, Live_8 and the Gamelan_01⁴ project. Since 2009 these pieces of software were no longer maintained.

The aim of E-Lab is the discovery of the morphological qualities of sound through the comparison between original and edited sounds, as well as the development of the skills to handle the sounds' morphology (Luca, 2009). Unlike DSP, the *concept* of E-Lab is not borrowed from screen-based mixer. Rather it is inspired by a matrix editing environment with a changeable set, that allows complex manipulations through the combination of easy transformations. It consists of an input area (Fig. 2, letter I) where the waveform is displayed and includes: playback controllers, the possibility to load stored sounds as well as to record audio streams and fade-in fade-out edit modes. Close to this area it is possible to store parameters in order to recall different sets (Fig. 2, letter P). The letters T correspond to the editing area where is possible to load up to three different modules. Eight modules are available:

- “Stirasuoni” for frequency and time domain transpositions.
- “Congelatore” based on a freezing technique.
- “Eco” to create rhythmic and melodic structures, based on a delay-harmonizer technique.
- “Massificatore” to create sound masses through a polyphonic reading technique.
- “Naviga-Suono” based on granular synthesis in order to explore the sound in any direction and at any speed.
- “Affiltratrice” a 256 band spectral domain filter.
- “Incrocia-Suoni” for the blending of two sound sources, based on the vocoder technique.
- “Riverbero” a reverb effect.

Figure 3. Live_8 screenshot.

The letter O corresponds to the output area where it is possible to display and save the outcome of the edit modules. This kind of approach to the learning environment ensures at least two advantages. First, reversibility: if the sound is processed through, for example, three modules (a, b, c) is possible to collect the result not only at the end of the process but also at an intermediate stage (e.g. between a and b). Second, visibility: for each and every transformation the result is represented through a real time graphical representation of the waveform in order to facilitate the consciousness of the alteration of the morphology of sound.

E-Lab was conceived to lead the students through the discovery of the physical qualities of sounds, whereas Live_8 is oriented to introduce them to become aware of the issues concerning the handling of the musical form. Live_8 is a *live* environment whereby is possible to edit, mix and launch up to eight different stored samples at the same time. The GUI is based on two devices: a keyboard-like area (Fig. 3 letters C1, C2, C3) with playback, gain and loop controllers, and a display for the representation of the waveform in time domain. Furthermore, it is possible to observe and to edit again the outcome of the mix (Fig. 3 letter O) as well as to save the configuration of the device (Fig. 3 letter M).

4.4. Compose with Sounds (CWS)

The software is a part of a wider initiative starting from the EARS pedagogical site⁵ (Landy, 2007, 2012). “*Compose with Sounds*” is an EU Culture program-funded software development project (2011-13) initiated by the Music, Technology and Innovation Centre at De Monfort University (UK). It involved partners in France (ina-GRM), Germany (ZKM) and Norway (NOTAM) as well as associate partners in Greece (EPHMEE/Ionian University in Corfu) and Portugal (Miso Music, Lisbon). The goal of the project was to lower the threshold for young composers who want to explore sound-based music and

⁴ *Gamelan_01* involved an orchestra of 80 children of 9 y.o. playing a real time electroacoustic composition developed during the preparatory workshops. It took place in 2007 at Teatro La Pergola, Florence. An excerpt of the performance is available at <http://vimeo.com/138252774>.

⁵ The ElectroAcoustic Resource Site (EARS) <http://ears2.dmu.ac.uk> is a dynamic eLearning site with a wide variety of hypermedia examples. It has been established to provide resources for those wishing to conduct research in the area of electroacoustic music studies as well as to introduce people of all ages, but especially those starting secondary education and their teachers, to the world of making music with sounds.

music composition, and to provide schools and individuals with an educational tool that encourages creativity, cross-cultural dialogue and the sharing of ideas and results”⁶.

CWS represents a necessary development of the basic assumption of the DSP project in the context of a more technologically mature situation as once increased processing power at cheaper price became available. Although the reference model of the screen-based mixer remains the same, and both projects do not support real-time processing of audio streams, CWS presents some desirable innovations and enhancements compared with its predecessor. The new GUI allows users an interaction with sound at five different levels:

- Sequencer: (Fig. 4 letter S) is the main window and the environment to handle and arrange the samples. It is composed of the sound library viewer, the time bar just below, an arrangement area and a control panel.
- Sound cards: the pictures displayed in the interactive sound library viewer window (Fig. 4 letter Sc) represent the sounds that can be used in a composition just

Figure 4. Compose with Sounds sequencer screenshot.

Figure 5. Delay viewer on the manipulation window.

by dragging them to the arrange area. It is possible to expand or build new libraries adding students’ own sounds.

- Edit modes: the controls (Fig. 4 letters E1, 2, 3) allows the user to change the way the sounds are displayed in the arrange area. E1 card mode, E2 waveform mode and E3 automation mode.
- Automation: the user can access the automation mode through the button (E3) or through the tiny picture above any samples in the arrange area. The mode allows the user to describe a pattern, with a break point curve (Fig. 4 letter A), for any parameter of the software.
- Manipulation window: it appears once the top of a card in the sequencer is double-clicked. The window is for adding and manipulating effects⁷, it contains a visualizer as well, which helps the student understanding the effect he or she is using (fig.5). All the tutorial texts and videos are linked to the pedagogical ElectroAcoustic Resource Site.

A number of schools in the six involved countries took part in this project. This has contributed to the further development of the software and teaching methodologies between 2011 and 2013. In order to secure a link with professional communities, composers worked alongside pupils resulting in the creation of a substantial number of works that were presented in concerts across Europe forming one of the key project outcomes⁸. Since 2013 the software is no longer maintained.

5. OBSERVATIONS

Despite different approaches to the critical issues of the concepts of the software these projects have granted some shared benefits to thousands of students involved in nine different countries. During the activities the majority of them developed a responsible and mindful attitude regarding their results, an increased critical sensibility and self-esteem, students with learning and relational difficulties also found the opportunity to express themselves positively emphasizing their characteristics (Luca, 2008).

Although these projects are no longer maintained (except the case of the EARS2 site), they undoubtedly have contributed to the creation of a school in Europe. In view of these experiences I suggest the following guidelines concerning future desirable developments.

- More than 30000 music apps are available on the *Apple App Store*, more than 3000 on *Google Play*, and making music on smart devices has been more than a simple novelty as already demonstrated by some excellent music apps like Audiobus, Beatsurfing, Mitosynth, SECTOR, SunVox, TC-11 and many more (Krebs, 2014, 2012). An up-to-date technological perspective should take into consideration the creation of educational apps

⁶ From the Compose With Sounds website: <http://cws.dmu.ac.uk/EN/11>.

⁷ A list of all effects and tutorial videos is available at http://cws.dmu.ac.uk/cwshelp/help_e/effects.html.

⁸ A selection of works composed by the students is available at <http://cws.dmu.ac.uk/EN/10>.

for smartphones and tablets instead of pieces of software for laptops and personal computers⁹. This fact presents more than one benefit. First, the software experience is enhanced not only through the touch screen, but also thanks to the possibility to use the sensors that are standard in such devices such as microphones, cameras, gyroscopes and compasses. Second, the learning environment is no longer constrained to the front of a screen and instead becomes *mobile*, stimulating the student, to explore the relation between movement and sound. Third, many students already own a smart device.

- The screen-based mixer approach should be abandoned in favor of a more informed perspective pointed towards the already existing commercial apps and more generally to the critical issues of the design-based researches (Aigner, 2015).
- A shared composition practice should be enhanced and based on standard orchestral practice, where each musician contributes to the creation of the performance by playing their part. The notable advantages of making music together are well known and cannot be discussed here, in any case apps or pieces of software that allow the students to work in group on the same composition in real time do not exist yet. This perspective should be carefully researched.

6. CONCLUSION

Technology has revolutionized how music in schools is taught, whilst the ways in which we access and listen to music through downloads, streaming libraries and smart devices have changed our engagement with it. Even though the response of music educators is not always ambitious or pedagogical and technologically up-to-date, it is clear that new media promise a longer and more durable interest in the subject. The ways to pass down the knowledge of the educational pieces of software for electroacoustic composition into the world of the smart devices has to be carefully devised. This new path has just begun.

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⁹ Interesting projects involving mostly primary school children have already taken place in Berlin, have a look at <http://app2music.de>.